

sodium peroxodisulphate (7 g.) in water (100 ml) was added dropwise, with vigorous stirring. To the resulting solution, acetic acid was added till pH comes just in the range of 3.7 to 4.0. The solution was boiled for an hour, left overnight and crystallised under vacuum when bright orange needle-shaped crystals of sodium 12-tungstomanganate(IV) separated which were recrystallised from hot water (Found: Na, 2.41; W, 60.99; Mn, 1.42; H, 1.85% Calcd. for $\text{Na}_4[\text{MnW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}] \cdot 32\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Na, 2.50; W, 61.14; Mn, 1.53; H, 1.85%). Hydrogen has been estimated by element estimation method and tungsten has been determined¹ by precipitating it as tungstic acid with HCl and cichonine hydrochloride, igniting it at 780° and finally weighing as WO_3 . Sodium was estimated by flame photometer and manganese was volumetrically determined by bismuthate method². From the analytical data, the molecular formula of the compound, as per Keggins's view³, comes out to be $\text{Na}_4[\text{MnW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}] \cdot 32\text{H}_2\text{O}$, which falls under the category of heteropoly compounds.

Molecular weight determinations: The cryoscopic method as has been applied successfully by Alexander⁴ and by Thilo and Kruger⁵ for molecular weight determinations of polymerised silicic acids, condensed phosphates, etc., in water and molten sodium sulphate decahydrate; has also been applied here for determination of approximate molecular weight of the compound. This determination showed the molecular weight of the polymeric compound to be 3470 as compared with the calculated value 3569.22. To know the accurate degree of polymerisation this result has been corroborated by X-ray crystal diffraction technique^{6,7} for molecular weight determination of heteropoly salts. The crystal diffraction data of the compound are $a=12.56$, $b=30.22$, $c=11.40$ and $\alpha=\beta=\gamma=90$, volume per unit cell $V=4327.02\text{Å}^3$. The space group is established as $D_{2h}^{24}-P_{nnn}$ from the following systematic presence of reflections: $hkl=\text{no condition}$; $0kl=k+l=2n$; $h0l=1+h=2n$; $hk0=h+k=2n$; $h00=(h=2n)$; $0k0=(k=2n)$; $001=1=2n$ and $hkl=h+k+l=2n$. The last condition gives the no. of molecules in unit cell (z) to be 2. Pycnometric measurement gives the observed density, $\rho_{\text{obs.}}=2.71 \text{ gml}^{-1}$. From the relation⁸, $\rho_{\text{obs.}}=1.66 \text{ M.Z/V}$, the molecular weight 'M' of the compound comes to 3646 against the calculated value 3569.22.

Determination of oxidation state of manganese ion: e.s.r. spectrum of heteropoly molybdomanganate and heteropoly tungstomanganate in frozen aqueous solution at 77 K have been measured. Both the compounds showed broad asymmetric signals with $g=3.8$. This is an expected value⁹ for a trigonally distorted d^5 ion. The effective magnetic moment of 12-sodium tungstomanganate(IV) was found by susceptibility measurements, the values being 3.88 B.M. at 302° and 3.89 B.M. at 77°K. Both the values are close to the spin-only for an $S=3/2$ ion, as expected⁹ for $3d^5$

system (three unpaired electrons), which definitely concludes that central heteroatom, Mn, is in +4 oxidation state.

Thermal depolymerization: The thermal depolymerization of the compound has been studied in the light of the investigations made by West and Audieth⁹ on a few heteropoly tungstic acid. Use was made of the apparatus described by Ray and Sinha¹⁰ with continuous pumping the depolymerised product, followed by successive weighing using a thermogravimetric balance and estimating at some stages. The dissociation⁶ of the compound was observed at 75° under reduced pressure when seven molecules of water was lost. At 140°, further twelve molecules of water were eliminated. The rest of water molecules remained intact in the crystal lattice till 290°, above which they were completely removed. When the temperature was raised still higher, then nearly at $480^\circ \pm 5^\circ$, the compound was broken as a whole into the basic units of lower oxides of tungsten and manganese which have been confirmed by analysis. So the thermal stability of sodium-12-tungstomanganate(IV) is $480^\circ \pm 50$.

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Formation Constants of Tl(I)-5-Nitro Salicylates and Effect of Nitro Substituent on the Formation Constants

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IN continuation to the previous work on Tl(I)-complexes of 3-Nitrosalicylic acid (3NSA)², and 3:5-Dinitrosalicylic acid (3:5 DNSA)³, the

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NOTES

proton-ligand formation constants and formation constants of 5-Nitrosalicylic acid (5NSA) with Tl(I) ion have been determined at 30°, using different computational methods viz. Half integral (HI), linear plot (LP), and point-wise calculation (PC), methods. Refined values of formation constants are obtained by the method of least-squares(LS).

To study the effect of the nitro substituent on the protonation and the stability of Tl(I)-complexes of salicylic acid with reference to its position, proton-ligand formation constants and formation constants of salicylic acid (SA) have also been determined under the same experimental conditions. Results with 3-NSA^a and 3 : 5-DNSA^a under the same experimental conditions, are already reported.

Experimental

pH-metric titrations of following sets were carried out at 30° :—

- (i) Free HClO₄
- (ii) free HClO₄+ligand and
- (iii) free HClO₄+ ligand +Tl(I), in 50% (V/V) aqueous thianol medium against standard NaOH solution while maintaining the ionic strength at 0.1 M NaClO₄.

The experimental set up and the method of calculation is the same as described earlier.

Results and Discussion

The Irving-Rossotti expression¹ was used for the calculation of $\bar{n}_A$, $\bar{n}$ and p(L). The values of log K_n^H and log K_n were directly recorded from the respective formation curves by half-integral method. Proton-ligand formation constants and formation constants of complexes are also calculated by linear

plot and point-wise calculation method using equation :—

$$\log K_n = p(L)_{n-\frac{1}{2}} \quad (\text{Ref. 8})$$

and

$$\log K_n^H = pH_{n-\frac{1}{2}}$$

Refined values of formation constants are obtained by the method of least squares. Values are recorded in Table 1.

The ratio of log K_1/K_2 is positive in both the cases. A difference between log K_1 and log K_2 is because of possible steric hindrance on the linking of the second ligand molecule.

In both the cases $\bar{n}$ value never exceeds 1.75, indicating thereby formation of only 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes. Estimation of elements in the complexes isolated, also indicates 1 : 2 ratio of metal to ligand in both the cases.

Effect of Nitro group :

The order of log K_1^H of the ligands used in the present investigation is : (Table 2)

and that of log K_2^H is :

where log K_1^H represents protonation with phenoxide group and log K_2^H , protonation with carboxylate group. The results are in agreement with the inductive and resonance effect of nitro group in each case.

The order of overall basicity (log K_β^H) is :

TABLE 1

PROTON-LIGAND FORMATION CONSTANTS AND FORMATION CONSTANTS OF Tl(I)-COMPLEXES

Method	Salicylic acid and its complexes						5-Nitrosalicylic acid and its complexes					
	log K_1^H	log K_2^H	log K_β^H	log K_1	log K_2	log K_β	log K_1^H	log K_2^H	log K_β^H	log K_1	log K_2	log K_β
HI	** (11.40)	3.21	14.61	8.95	5.00	13.95	10.76	2.28	13.04	8.28	5.44	13.72
LP	12.00	3.20	15.20	8.95	5.02	13.97	10.76	2.28	13.04	8.28	5.43	13.71
PC	12.29	3.20	15.49	8.75	5.07	13.82	10.76	2.20	12.96	8.29	5.45	13.74
LS				8.94	5.12	14.06				8.29	5.43	13.72

** Value is calculated from log K_β^H

TABLE 2

PROTON-LIGAND FORMATION CONSTANTS OF LIGANDS FORMATION CONSTANTS OF Tl(I)-COMPLEXES

	log K_1^H	log K_2^H	log K_β^H	log K_1	log K_2	log K_β
	SA	11.73	3.20	14.93	8.90	5.05
3-NSA	10.34	2.30	13.64	7.87	5.05	12.92
5-NSA	10.75	2.26	13.01	8.28	5.44	13.72
3 : 5-DNSA	8.17	2.04	10.21	6.21	4.38	10.59

The order of formation constants of Tl(I)-complexes (Table 2) is :

This is in agreement with the basicities of the ligands. Decrease in the stabilities of the complexes, is in agreement with the expectation of steric effect^{4,5} of nitro substituent for Tl(I) ion in each case because of its large size and position in different ligands.

Results indicate the failure of Hammett's equation⁶ and Taft's equation⁷ in the ligands as well as in complexes.

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Letter to the Editor

Dear Sir,

Recently we have come across a paper entitled, "Mossbauer Studies on some Fe(III) complexes" by C. L. Sharma, Ashok Kumar Singh and Lakshmi Devi¹ published in this journal. In this connection we would like to point out that we have published in 1970 a paper entitled, "Mossbauer Studies on some iron(III) complexes".² The complexes investigated by us included [Fe(Saccharin)₂Cl], K[Fe(3-nitro-phthalimide)₂CH₃OH] and [Fe(benzofuryl carboximide-N-p-toluenesulphonyl)₂]. Though the complexes investigated by Sharma *et al*¹ are naturally different, there is a considerable overlap in the language employed in the recent paper as compared to ours. In fact at a number of places in the text their paper appears to be a verbatim copy of our paper except that the names of the complexes are different, although our paper has not been cited by them.

We are thankful to the Hon. Editor for giving us an option to present our views.

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